

Education Quarterly Reviews

Göksoy, Süleyman. (2021), Principals' Positive Organizational Behavior in Schools and Its Results. In: *Education Quarterly Reviews*, Vol.4 Special Issue 1: Primary and Secondary Education, 99-110.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.04.02.230

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Principals' Positive Organizational Behavior in Schools and Its Results

Süleyman Göksoy¹

¹ Düzce University, Düzce, Turkey. ORCID: 0000-0002-7151-0863

Correspondence: Süleyman Göksoy, Düzce University, Faculty of Education, Educational Sciences, Educational Administration and Supervision, 81600, Düzce/ TURKEY, Email: suleymangoksoy@duzce.edu.tr

Abstract

In this study, the positive situations that principals put forward about teachers, students, the institution and themselves, and the results of these positive situations and practices were investigated. The current study has been carried out with a descriptive purpose. The positive organizational behavior of the principals in schools and its results, which is the subject of the study, are examined within the scope of "phenomenology." The research was conducted on 32 different institutions and educators in a province in the Western Black Sea Region in the 2020-2021 academic year. In the present study, it has been obtained that the principals generally emphasize the positive organizational behaviors of teachers, students, the school and themselves. Considering the fact that positive organizational behavior in schools increases corporate and individual performance and highlights the strengths of the organization and employees, the following comment can be made: Educational institutions and managers need to make positive organizational behavior a part of the corporate culture and corporate climate.

Keywords: School, Positive Organizational Behavior, Principal

1. Introduction

Organizations are social entities whose activities are consciously structured and coordinated, connected with the external environment, towards specific goals. Organizations bring together material and human resources to achieve desired goals and results. They produce goods and services efficiently. They allow to come true new discoveries. They use modern production and information technologies. They adapt to the changing environment and at the same time affect that environment. The organizations create value for its customers and employees. They manage difficult issues such as employee motivation, coordination, ethics and diversity (Daft, 2015). Organizational behavior is a discipline that tries to understand the reasons for the attitudes and behaviors of individuals within the organization, to control and predict these attitudes and behaviors, and to create conditions that can ensure the happiness of individuals in the workplace. Organizational behavior is a branch that researches the effects of individuals, groups and structures on behavior within the organization in order to improve the efficiency of the organization. Organizational behavior focuses on the questions of how it happens and how

much the effects of individuals, groups and organizational structures on individual behaviors within the organization in order to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization (Robbins & Judge, 2012).

Today, institutions are under pressure of a progressively increasing competitive. Some of the basic questions that organizations ask to be successful in a competitive environment are: How can organizations reveal people's strengths? How can the potential of individuals be increased? How can dynamism and flexibility in the organization be developed? These questions, which are focused and whose answers are researched, fall into the field of positive organizational learning (positive organizational behavior). Luthans and Youssef (2007; as cited in Robbins & Judge, 2012) state that in their researches, the negative and wrong behaviors of those employees in organizations are mostly focused. However they state that it is necessary to be highlighted their positive and best strengths, be approached with a positive perspective and be viewed from a positive perspective for the company and its employees. Thus, it is emphasized that the performance of employees increases, they develop more and become stronger, and as a result of all these, they contribute to organizational goals and organizational outputs. Therefore, it can be said that managers in institutions should focus on the good and strong aspects with their positive features of the employees.

Positive organizational behavior follows a recent positive psychology that focuses on the strengths and psychological capacities of individuals and is guided by research and theories (Luthans, 2002; as cited in Özen Kutanis & Yıldız, 2014). Positive organizational behavior is also within the subject of social psychology. Social psychology is the scientific study of how people think about each other, how they affect each other, and how they relate to each other (Myers, 2017). Positive organizational behavior was born out of positive psychology and used the scientific method. Positive organizational behavior is mainly concerned with the issue of personal psychological qualities and their influence on the development of performance. The concepts they are interested in are topics like self-efficiency, hope, optimism, resilience, positive psychological capital, trust, and extroversion (Luthans, Youssef & Avolio, 2006). It is seen that highlighting the positive, well-done strengths of the employees of the institution, approaching their behavior with a positive perspective increases the performance of the employees, they develop and become stronger and it increases simply the quality of organizational outputs. This situation can be explained with social impact theory in one way. Social impact is the changes that occur in a person's behavior by being affected by the judgments, attitudes and opinions of another person or people (Güney, 2016). In addition, positive organizational behavior is also compatible with the expectation theory in motivation. Motivation expectation theory emphasizes that positive expectations from individuals increase their success and also reduce their anxiety. Various research findings have been obtained showing that students in schools where teachers have positive and high expectations about the students are more successful than other schools (Slavin, 2013).

One of the important concepts of social learning theory, which is closely related to positive organizational behavior, is self-efficiency. Self-efficiency describes a person's belief in the power to perform a task (Robbins & Judge, 2012). Self-efficiency is the feeling of self-efficiency and competence, unlike self-respect which means self-esteem (Myers, 2017). Self-efficiency is people's beliefs, judgments and thoughts about their own capacity to do a job well, to solve a problem, to acquire a skill. It can be given an example such as a math teacher believing that he can teach algebra successfully to his students. Therefore, individuals who have strong beliefs about their own abilities are more successful and more persistent in their efforts (Hoy & Miskel, 2012). Naturally, people with high self-efficiency are not afraid to try new things (Senemoğlu, 1997). Individuals with high self-efficiency can cope with complex events, overcome problems, be more patient and become more successful (Korkmaz, 2006). For this reason, it is necessary to organize activities to improve the self-efficiency of people from childhood and to provide training in this context.

As tried to explain above, positive organizational behavior refers to positive behaviors that contribute to the goals of the organization and positive organizational outcomes. Therefore, organizational behavior should be viewed from a positive perspective. Supportive, affirmative and close relationships should be developed in order to increase positive organizational behavior in institutions. So, increasing positive feelings increase both health and happiness (Myers, 2017). School administrators have important responsibilities in this regard. School administrators should benefit from both the strengths of educators at school and they should be able to reveal the

strengths of educators. For this, school administrators should have a positive perspective towards human behavior.

How do we affect other people or how are we affected by other people? The purpose of asking those questions is important both to increase the happiness of the individual in the workplace and to increase the performance of individuals and groups. The questions on which organizational behavior focuses are as follows: How and how much effective are factors such as personality, self, attitude, stress, perception, emotion, age, gender, seniority, education, expectation, motivation, and goal in increasing the performance of the organization and the individual? How much is the formation of teams, task distribution, communication, social, cultural relations, job descriptions in order to improve and increase corporate performance (corporate effectiveness, efficiency) and how does it affect individual behaviors (performance of the individual) within the organization?

In the present study, what is wanted to be researched and learned is whether school administrators have a positive perspective towards human behavior in their institutions. In this context, the research focused on the following questions:

- Is the behavior of individuals (school, teacher, student, employee) in the institution viewed from a positive perspective by school administrators?
- Are the strengths of employees emphasized by school administrators and these aspects highlighted?
- In which situations do school administrators exhibit more positive behaviors?
- What are the consequences of the positive behavior of school administrators?

2. Method

The research was conducted for descriptive purposes. In descriptive understanding, the researcher defines, classifies, lists, or categorizes events and their relationships to describe mental processes and behavior (Shaughnessy, Zechmeister & Zechmeister; 2020). The study was based on qualitative research methods and techniques. The research was planned according to the phenomenological (phenomenological) pattern. The positive organizational behavior and results of the school principal subject to the study were examined within the scope of "phenomenology." The process of "phenomenology," also called phenomenological study, helps to reveal and interpret individual perceptions and at the same time aims to investigate the phenomena that we are not completely alien to but still cannot fully understand (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008).

2.1 Study Group/Participants

The research was applied in the 2020-2021 academic year. In the research, maximum diversity sampling was preferred. Demographic characteristics of the participants are shown in Table 1

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the participants

Field	The participant Teacher		
	Field	Female (14)	Male (18)
Mission	<i>Teacher</i>	11	16
	<i>Assistant Principals</i>	3	2
Level of Education	<i>Bachelor's Level</i>	12	16
	<i>Post-graduate Education</i>	2	2
Teaching Seniority	<i>1-5</i>	1	1
	<i>6-10</i>	4	8
	<i>11-15</i>	6	5
	<i>Above 16</i>	3	4
Place of Duty	<i>Kindergarten</i>	3	
	<i>Primary School</i>	5	9
	<i>Secondary School</i>	3	4
	<i>High School</i>	3	5
Total		14	18

The research was carried out on 32 *assistant* principals and teachers working in different educational institutions (preschool, primary school, secondary school and high school) in a province in the Western Black Sea Region. Attention was paid to include participants from equal education levels in the research.

2.2 Data Collection and Data Collection Tools

Qualitative research is a process in which many data collection methods such as observation, interview and document analysis used and the perceptions and events revealed in a realistic and holistic manner in the natural environment (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008). In this context, data were collected using the interview form and document analysis methods. In the preparation of the interview form, firstly the literature review was made. A draft interview form with ten items was created. Two academicians, a teacher and a school principal for content validity, and a Turkish teacher to determine language proficiency were interviewed. Before giving the final form to the interview form, a pre-interview was held with three teachers. As a result of the feedback received as a result of the pre-interviews, five questions containing demographic information were added to the interview form, and a semi-structured interview form consisting of four main questions and two sub-questions under each question was formed.

During the data collection process of the study, due to the pandemic, the interview form was obtained via e-mail and, when necessary, calls were made by mobile phone to make explanations. Participants were given code names such as E1, E2, E3,... The questions that constitute the Semi-Structured interview form are:

1) *Are generally your negative and wrong aspects, your behaviors or your strengths and behaviors that you do best emphasized by your school administrator?*

- *In which situations are your positive or negative aspects and behaviors more prominent at school?*

- *What kind of consequences does highlighting your positive or negative aspects and behaviors at school have?*

2) *Are generally the negative and wrong aspects, behaviors, or strengths and behaviors of the students highlighted by your school administrator?*

- *Applications in which positive or negative behaviors of students to be highlighted at school.*

- *The results of the positive or negative behaviors of students to be highlighted at school*

3) *Are the negative and wrong aspects of the school in general or the strengths and behaviors of your school that it does the best highlighted by your school administrator?*

- Applications highlighted positive or negative aspects in school.
 - The results of highlighted the positive or negative aspects in school
- 4) Does your school principal generally emphasize his / her negative and wrong aspects, behaviors, or his / her best strengths and behaviors?
- Situations and practices in which the school administrator highlights positive or negative behaviors about him / her
 - The results of the school principal's highlighting positive or negative behaviors about himself/herself

2.3 Data Analysis

Content analysis technique was used in the analysis of the research data. Content analysis is a systematic analysis of written and oral materials. Content analysis can be defined as the process of coding what people say and write according to clear instructions (Simon & Burstein, 1985; cited in Balci, 2010). Therefore, the data have been conceptualized, categorized, interpreted and presented. The stages followed in the study are generally as follows: transcribing the interview data sent via mail, organizing the written data, determining the concepts and expressions to be analysed, accessing key concepts from concepts and expressions, creating categories, analysing and explaining the data according to the specified categories and concepts; explaining, interpreting and presenting suggestions supported by direct quotations.

2.4 Reliability and Validity

The data collection process of the research was carried out and recorded in the e-mail environment in order to ensure the credibility, transferability, consistency and verifiability of the research within the scope of validity and reliability. Attention was paid to behaving objectively at all stages of the research. Care was taken to provide detailed information in the analysis of the data. Explanatory information is given in the method part of the study. The opinions of the participants in the study were presented in the findings section without comment and generalization. In order to ensure the verifiability of the study, it was explained in detail how the data were collected, the data were recorded and interpreted.

3. Results

It has been investigated what the positive situations highlighted by school administrators, teachers, students, the institution and themselves, as well as the results of positive situations and practices. 32 educators working at different educational levels participated in the study. The educators participating in the study stated that the school administrator generally exhibits positive organizational behavior. In this context, the research results have been categorized and interpreted under the following headings.

- Positive behaviors towards teachers at school and their consequences
- Positive behaviors towards students at school and their consequences
- Positive behaviors towards school and their consequences
- The positive behavior of the school administrator towards himself and its results.

3.1 a. Situations that the school administrator highlights best works of teachers and his / her strengths

School administrators generally emphasize the strengths of teachers and offer various opportunities to teachers in schools. For example, the administrator takes into account the strengths of teachers in effective implementation of teaching, methods and techniques, distribution of duties and responsibilities, use of technology, organization preparation, planning, programming, activities, group work, board meetings, developing education, scanning the field, and providing educational support. S/he supports projects. S/he appreciates the teachers by giving positive feedback. However, it is stated that school administrators should acknowledge teachers very well in order to highlight their strengths by the educators who participated in the study. It is also recommended that personal behavior should not be generalized.

3.1.b The results of the school principal's highlighting the strengths of the teachers that teachers do best:

School administrators encourage teachers to do new studies as a result of emphasizing the strengths of teachers in general, supporting them and appreciating them. This encouragement creates an objective, collaborative school climate. It both increases motivation and keeps it constantly alive. Communication within the school increases. School and teacher success increases. At school, a sense of we, not me, is created.

The answers given by the educators who participated in the research to this question are as follows:

In order for the education and training process to be more effective and the teacher to take a more functional role at this stage, our school administrator generally reveals more strengths and behaviors of us teachers. For example, in the educational environment, the strengths of teachers are mostly determinant in the distribution of duties and responsibilities. In another example, when our school principal assigns tasks or responsibilities to a technology-savvy teacher in school based on this strong characteristic, teachers' self-confidence increases and they become self-aware. In addition, the school administration, which deals with the wrong aspects of us educators from time to time, actually contributes to professional development in identifying our negative behaviors and providing the necessary support as well as knowing the strengths of the educators for the realization of education (E1). It highlights my strengths rather than what I do best. Just like the organization giving me the task of preparing for any organization to be held at the school. Like asking me to lead my other classmates in activities related to my field (E2). Good and good attitudes and behaviors are supported. Warnings are made in the appropriate language (E3). He reads the student progress reports and gives positive feedback (E4). Our school administrator highlights our strengths and behaviors that we educators generally do best. To give a concrete example, it always supports all kinds of work done for the benefit of the school and students. This support and appreciation of our manager encourage us teachers to do new studies. In the field surveys conducted recently in our school, teachers supported the colleagues in every subject and always appreciated the work done (E5). In order for our school administrators to know our strengths and weaknesses, first of all, they should know us well. A school administrator who does not know his staff well, unfortunately evaluates the educators according to the daily events. Our strengths are generally addressed to our institution. For example, the success of any teacher in the board meeting can be cited as an example (E6). Our school principal makes an objective explanation to us on this issue. It offers us suggestions on how to change our negative or wrong behavior. It always keeps our motivation high by highlighting the behaviors we do best (E7). It highlights my strengths more. Since our school is a vocational high school, many activities and activities are carried out. It is very important to establish School Industry cooperation. Last year, he commissioned me in the organization of our school's industry-school meeting. It was a very effective program. Planning the organization, inviting the participants, and leaving the program entirely under my coordination, gave me the opportunity to reveal my strengths (E8). Our principal highlights our positive and strengths / behaviors. In fact, I have witnessed many times that he used the expression "us" instead of "me" in the successes of our school where he was the pioneer. In incomplete or unfavourable situations, he undertakes the fault / fault himself and does not hurt the fault / mistake of the defective person, does not succumb to his personal ambitions and offend. Usually he tries to solve the situation in the most positive way possible for everyone (E9). Like a fellow teacher bringing his mistake to the agenda at every meeting and not commenting on the pleasurable situations that have developed (E10). Our school administrator always supports the implementation of teaching methods and techniques, communication within the school, and the successful fulfilment of our duties (E11). Students' successful results and positive behaviors are expressed in mock exams (T12). Our school principal attaches great importance to a positive school climate and cooperation. This approach creates a positive environment in the school (T13). Like a fellow teacher bringing his mistake to the agenda at every meeting and not commenting on the pleasurable situations that develop (E14). Generally, he assigns them to jobs that everyone thinks they can do according to their abilities (E15). My school principal always appreciates the work we have done, for example, during this epidemic. He talks about the good work we do in the general teachers' board meeting (E17). I am a Visual Arts teacher, thanks to the teachers' board meeting after my work, and praise me and my work (E18). He congratulates me verbally when I have good changes and success with my class or students (E19). He discovers that people in general have the intention and effort to work and makes it easy for him. For example, it supports me when I think I am doing my job properly, and helps when I need any help (E20).

3.2.a Situations where the school administrator the best works of students and highlights their strengths

There are lots of strengths and positive aspects of the students in school principal's school. Some of them are those; He gives tasks to students who can speak effectively in school programs. S/he provides opportunities for students with sportive success. These behaviors of students who display positive behavior are appreciated. The activities and skills that students do best are highlighted. Success is rewarded. Constructive criticism is made. Talented students are discovered. . S/he meets with the children one to one. . S/he provides materials suitable for children. . S/he organizes a wide variety of activities for students. . S/he tells them the good behavior of the child. . S/he provides financial support. However, it is also recommended that effective communication with students is required.

3.2.b The results of highlighting the positive aspects of the students whose the school administrator

As a result of emphasizing the strengths and positive aspects of the students in *the school administrator's* school, the quality of education increases. Students' behavior improves. Students realize themselves. Self-confidence and self-perception increase in students. They gain the necessary skills. Students act in accordance with the values. Problems are solved with an understanding of cooperation. Students become aware of their own abilities. Students feel comfortable and safe themselves. It helps teachers in the teaching-learning process. It prepares students for life. Students feel valued themselves.

The answers given by the educators who participated in the research to this question are as follows:

Our school administrator generally engages in activities that will highlight the strengths and behaviors of the students. For example, evaluating students with strong and effective speaking skills in school programs and students with strong sportive skills in this field gives very effective results. Our school administrator encourages the students to use their strengths and ensures that the product is of higher quality in education and that individuals realize themselves. Evaluating their strengths more predominantly helps students gain self-esteem (E1). Providing and providing appropriate materials for students. It organizes a wide variety of activities for students (E2). Our school administrator prepares students for life by bringing the positive aspects of the students to the forefront (E3). Strives for students to feel valued. It gives them financial and moral support (E4). MYZ My school is a school for disabled students. Our school principal attaches great importance to revealing the strengths and behaviors of our students and providing them with the necessary skills to continue their lives in the future without the need for anyone. The best example for this is the observation of students' skills in the 9th grade and placing them in the fields according to their skills in the 10th grade (E5). Our school administrator highlights the strengths and behaviors that students generally do best. To give a concrete example, we definitely announce every positive behavior that our students do in the school environment or outside, and that is in accordance with our values, at the National Anthem ceremonies, in order to take as an example for all our students. This situation positively affects our other students (E6). Our school administrator constantly reveals the positive aspects and thus increases the self-confidence of the students. In this case, students feel themselves in a comfortable and safe environment (E7). At our institution, students' strong and best jobs come to the fore. In particular, problems related to students are resolved with the cooperation of the psychological counsellor, guidance counsellor and parents. National and international achievements of students are rewarded (E8). Our school administrator takes care that our students must always be in line with a successful student profile. Makes constructive criticism of students on this issue (E9). Supports our students to highlight their strengths and behaviors. He enabled one of our unsuccessful students to demonstrate their talent in the field of sports and to prove themselves by giving them the necessary support (E10). As our school principal / administrators, we generally prefer to focus on the positive aspects. Since we are a vocational high school, the expectations of both the environment and the teachers of our school from the students are very low. However, we believe that each of our students is skilled and has aspects that need to be highlighted / discovered, and we emphasize this idea each time (E11). Usually, his communication with students is about misbehaviour. The communication process is completed by finding suggestions to prevent these behaviors (E12). Since pre-school education is continuous, children are always with their teachers. With the school administration, families, and teachers, children are made to behave positively (E13). Our school administrator meets with the children one-on-one in order to highlight the positive behaviors of the children. He tells the boy's good behavior to him. It helps the teacher (E15). Usually, his communication with students is about misbehaviour. The communication process is completed by making suggestions to prevent these behaviors (E16). It expresses that our students should always

be supported and that they are the future of us and our country. It works for vocational high school students to change the perspective of the environment (E17). My school principal appreciates those who have academic talent for their academic achievement, makes medals and rewards them. He tries to highlight these features of those who are talented in sports or fine arts and directs them (E18). He congratulates the children on the success they have achieved in the competition and often gives them a book, etc. rewards with things (E19). Emphasizes what students can do. It acts according to its potential. It contributes to the communication and social aspects of the student and their parents. For example; prefers to reward successful students in sports by advancing them in the field of sports. It also supports academically good students in this direction and talks with the student's classroom teacher and parents (E20).

3.3.a Situations and practices where the school administrator does the best and highlights the strengths of the school

Strengths and practices highlighted in the school are to have sufficient resources, the educators being effective, motivating, and the management unit being open to innovative developments. The products made by the students are shared with the environment of the school. The activities and projects carried out by them are published on the school website. The beautiful works of the school are exhibited, promoted and shared on social media. Precautions are taken beforehand for possible negative effects. The cleaning of the school is its internal and external security. However, it is recommended that importance and priority should be given not only to the academic achievements of the school principal but also to the development of relations with the school environment and employment areas.

3.3.b The results of positive situations/ practices highlighted at school

As a result of revealing the positive aspects of the school: suitable strategies for education and instruction are found and used. It provides coordination among school stakeholders. The strategic goals of the school are achieved. All teachers at the school work diligently, devotedly and make great efforts. The school has received a total quality certificate.

The answers given by the educators who participated in the research to this question are as follows:

Our school administrator finds the right strategy for the educational environment by revealing both the negative and strengths of our educational institution at the same rate. For example, the finding that the classroom corridors and common education areas of our school lack sufficient educational materials reveals a negative side of the school and also its strong side by emphasizing that there is an environment that has the potential to overcome this deficiency. Our school administrator also makes use of the strengths of the institution in achieving strategic goals. The most emphasized strengths of our institution are the sufficient resources, the effective and motivating staff of the educators, and the openness of the administrative unit to innovative developments (E1). It is the only school that has received a quality certificate within the scope of total quality management at the provincial level (E2). Rather, it reveals the strengths that our school does and has the best. For example, sharing the products made by our students with the environment of the school and exhibiting that our school is doing good work. Such as promoting school activities through social media (E3). Our school administrator is someone who praises the positive aspects of our school and makes an effort to increase these aspects. In this way, it conducts a coordinated study with all stakeholders of the school (E4). He takes an active role in projects that concern our school and includes them in pictures, videos, etc. shares them with images on social media or on the school site (E5). The achievements and strengths of our ÖG School stand out. For example, success in mock exams is seen as the strength of the school (E15). Our school administrator highlights the strengths that our school generally does best. To give a concrete example, all teachers in our school work selflessly. Everyone makes a great effort for our school and our students to continue their education and training activities under the best conditions. Our manager always makes his support felt everywhere, with all the means he can in these matters (E16). In my opinion, no manager wants to highlight the weaknesses of his institution. Usually, it brings the institution to the forefront in areas where it is strong. Of course, it takes measures in the weaknesses or tries to improve. The news we share on social media can be an example of this (E17). Although our school administrator is not satisfied with the physical structure of our school (the number of classrooms is small), he can tolerate this negative situation as much as possible. It reveals the strengths of our school (E18). Our school administrator generally highlights the positive and strong aspects of the school. It reminds us of the good work

we do in any situation / environment where positive / negative issues about our school come up, and emphasizes that we strive for better work and that we need to work with determination (E19). Since our school is a Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School, we can come forward with our stronger sides in the areas in our school. However, since our principal is not in the profession, he is trying to bring the school to the forefront, which is only focused on academic success. Unfortunately, it causes us to come to the fore with a negative aspect, not high, in our academic success. However, by opening a revolving fund in our school, it can produce products from fields to industry, it can be more effective in training qualified personnel for the sector. By actively interacting with the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, we can become a school that trains the staff the sector is looking for (E20). In general, we develop and strengthen these aspects of our work by taking an opinion on the works that are good and good. Before negative behaviors, measures are taken to prevent possible negativities. The activities and projects carried out are published on the school website (E21). Especially the cleanliness of the school and its internal and external security come to the fore (E22). It states that our school is a well-established school and should always be protected. Our school organizes an alumni meeting every year in cooperation with the Alumni Association (E23). Our school was not a school that prepared many students for the Fine Arts and Sports High School, when our principal came, he started the necessary work to prepare students for these high schools (E24). It enables us to discover the strengths of our school in general and contributes to the positive corporate culture of the school by organizing students, teachers and parents on these issues. For example; organizes social and cultural activities that can be done in our school, conducts interviews in the name of corporate culture and healthy communication, expresses that he values such issues (E25).

3.4.a Situations and practices in which the school administrator highlights positive behaviors about himself/herself

The situation is to be determined to leadership, guidance, effective speaking, ethical behavior and in decisions. S/he can communicate effectively, empathize, and act in accordance with the rules of courtesy. S/he can be just and respectful. S/he supports change efforts. S/he makes the right decisions for the effectiveness and efficiency of the institution. S/he uses a democratic and participatory management system. S/he makes use of school resources and educator elements. Being open to criticism is that s/he can also criticize himself when necessary.

3.4.b The results of the school principal's highlighting his/her positive behaviors about himself/herself

It creates a motivating education environment. S/he always improves himself/herself. The artistic aspect stands out. Being open to developments and trying to eliminate deficiencies. Trying to correct negative behaviors and taking responsibility in negative situations. It is the increase of general culture. However, it is also suggested that the school administrator should give more voice to the employees of the institution in order to increase the positive results about himself/herself.

The answers given by the educators who participated in the research to this question are as follows:

Our school administrator generally highlights his positive and strengths. For example, having an effective leadership role, insistence on ethical behavior, supporting change efforts in the school, taking the right decisions for the effectiveness and efficiency of the institution, gaining competence with postgraduate education and supportive education, adopting the idea that teaching is essential in the profession, all units in the school are on the denominator of good product output. To unite, to use democratic and participatory management system, to benefit from school resources and educator elements to achieve school goals, to create a motivating educational environment for the student and the teacher to realize himself, in short, to continuously improve himself to manage an educational institution effectively and efficiently it is a concrete indicator of using it more dominantly (E1). It is a role model (E2). Our principal often finds it appropriate to express his best or achievements (E3). My school administrator generally focuses on strengths (E4). In general, our school director focuses on his / her strengths and ensures that he / she can talk and move forward. For example, when talking about himself in a meeting or meeting, he expresses what he can do and acts in accordance with his character structure. (E5). It finds sponsors and proudly shares with us the educational materials provided free of charge to the school. He shares with us the achievements he has achieved and the thoughts he plans to make in his mind, and explains how useful projects are for the school and students (E6). I think he is a fair, respectful manager with empathy skills (E23). Our principal emphasizes the strengths that he does best. For example; I think he has a strong character in terms of his management position. Also, because his branch is painting, it has an artistic

side. It definitely has an artistic touch in the events and organizations to be held at the school. Like decoration (E24). Our school administrator is open to criticism. He is someone who can respond to all comments, good or bad, with maturity. Since our manager is open to developments, I do not think he would be uncomfortable hearing or expressing them when they have negative aspects (E25). Our school principal highlights his / her best performance or strengths. Human nature tries to hide negativity. He is aware of his own shortcomings and tries to improve them (E26). Our school administrator can criticize himself when necessary. It is quite natural for him to bring himself to the forefront in the works he has done and put a lot of effort into. However, he can criticize himself when necessary. He tries to correct his negative behaviors (E27). My School Principal highlights his strengths. My principal's strongest aspect is his preaching. It tries to guide students or teachers by talking about education, school, environment, student. Its general culture is quite good (E28). He underlines his positive aspects in general. However, when there is a negative situation about the school, he questions himself, his mistakes / deficiencies rather than the other. For example, his own speech, without giving the other party the right to speak at any meeting (29E). Our ÖG Manager often finds it appropriate to express his best or achievements (E30). Our school administrator is a kind, polite person who has a leading role in communicating with us. He is frank and sensitive (E31). Our school principal can change and update the curriculum if there is an error or a situation that may be better (E32).

4. Discussion

Positive psychology holds that we should deal with the positive aspects of human behavior rather than the negative aspects. The reflection of positive psychology understanding to the corporate environment is positive organizational behavior. In the present study, which investigated the results of positive organizational behaviors and positive organizational behavior of school administrators, it was obtained that the school administrator generally emphasizes the positive organizational behaviors of teachers, students, the school and themselves. These features are given in detail below.

4.1 School administrators highlight their strengths

4.1.a Situations about teachers

The school administrator offers a variety of opportunities to teachers in schools. S/he takes into account the strengths of teachers in effective implementation of teaching methods and techniques, distribution of duties and responsibilities, use of technology, organization preparation, planning, programming, activities, group studies, board meetings, developing education, scanning the field, and providing educational support. S/he supports projects. S/he appreciates the teachers and the students by giving positive feedback.

4.1.b Situations about students

S/he gives tasks to students who can speak effectively in school programs. S/he provides opportunities for students with sportive success. These behaviors of students who display positive behavior are appreciated. The activities and skills that students do best are highlighted. Success is rewarded. Constructive criticism is made. Talented students are discovered. S/he meets with the children one to one. S/he provides materials suitable for children. S/he organizes a wide variety of activities for students. S/he tells them the good behavior of the child. S/he provides financial support.

4.1.c Situations about school

Having sufficient resources, the educators being effective, motivating, and the management unit being open to innovative developments. The products made by the students are shared with the environment of the school. The activities and projects carried out are published on the school website. The beautiful works of the school are exhibited, promoted and shared on social media. Precautions are taken beforehand for possible negative effects. Trial exam results. The cleaning of the school is its internal and external security.

4.1.d Situations about the school administrator herself/himself

Leadership, guidance, effective speaking, ethical behavior and determination in decisions. They can communicate effectively, empathize, and act in accordance with the rules of courtesy. He can be just and

respectful. It is to support change efforts. It is to make the right decisions for the effectiveness and efficiency of the institution. It uses a democratic and participatory management system. It is to make use of school resources and educator elements. Being open to criticism is that he can also criticize himself when necessary.

4.2 School administrators highlight their strengths

4.2.a Results about teachers

As a result of his/her support and appreciation of teachers, s/he encourages teachers to do new studies. S/he creates an objective, collaborative school climate. S/he both increases motivation and keeps it constantly alive. Communication within the school increases. School and teacher success increases. At school, a sense of we, not me, is created. As Tugade and Fredrickson (2004) stated, positive emotions broaden the person's perspective cognitively (As cited in Narcıkara, 2017). Similarly, Luthans (2002; as cited in Özen Kutanis & Oruç, 2014) states that positive organizational behavior includes the development of existing employees and increasing their performance.

4.2.b Results about the students

The quality of education increases. Students' behavior improves. Students realize themselves. Self-confidence and self-perception increase in students. They gain the necessary skills. Students act in accordance with the values. Problems are solved with an understanding of cooperation. Students become aware of their own abilities. Students feel comfortable and safe themselves. It helps teachers in the teaching-learning process. It prepares students for life. Students feel valued themselves. Similar results were obtained in the research conducted by Şanlı (2009). According to the results of the research, it has been observed that the rate of bringing students to higher education is higher in schools where school principals who adopt a positive management approach and manage the school.

4.2.c Results about school

Correct and suitable strategies are found and used for education and instruction. It provides coordination among school stakeholders. The strategic goals of the school are achieved. All teachers at the school work diligently, devotedly and make great efforts. The school has received a quality certificate. Similarly, Güler and Saripek (2014; as cited in Tösten, 2015) stated that positive organizational behavior brings a higher commitment to the mission, values and goals of the organization, and employees are more willing, productive and collaborative while in a positive psychology.

4.2.d Results about the school administrator herself/himself

S/he creates a motivating education environment. It is constantly improving himself/herself. The artistic aspect stands out. Being open to developments and trying to eliminate deficiencies. Trying to correct negative behaviors and taking responsibility in negative situations. It is the increase of general culture. However, it is also suggested that the school administrator should give more voice to the employees of the institution in order to increase the positive results about himself.

As stated by Özen Kutanis and Yıldız (2014), emphasizing the positive aspects of people instead of their negative aspects helps to contribute to more effective human resources practices. The results of emphasizing the positive aspects and behaviors of the teachers, students, the school and himself in general also show consistency with the results of the school administrators' emphasized by Luthans, Youssef and Avolio (2006; as cited in Özen Kutanis & Oruç, 2014): Self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience. The present results also support the thesis of Cameron, Dutton, and Quinn (2003) that positive emotions cause people to experience continuous and more positive emotions and to achieve positive outcomes, such as positive spirals that rise by influencing and expanding people's thinking behaviors and habits (Akt. Narcıkara, 2017).

Acknowledgments

When considering the positive organizational behavior in schools, increasing the institutional and individual performance and emphasizing the strengths of the institution and its employees, it can be said that educational institutions and managers should make positive organizational behavior a part of the corporate culture and

corporate climate. School administrators should approach employees and events with a positive perspective. The positive, best, and strengths of the organization and its employees should be brought forward. In addition, it is necessary that importance and priority should be given not only to the academic achievements of the school administrator, but also to the development of relations with the school environment and employment areas. It is stated by the educators who participated in the study that school administrators should know the teachers and students very well in order to highlight their strengths. It is also recommended that personal behavior should not be generalized.

References

- Balcı, A. (2010). Sosyal bilimlerde araştırma [Research in social sciences] Ankara, Turkey, Pegem Akademi
- Daft, Richard L. (2015). Örgüt kuramları ve tasarımını anlamak. [Understanding organizational theories and design] (Ed. Ömür N. Timurcanday Özmen). Ankara, Turkey, Nobel Publications.
- Güney, S. (2016). Örgütsel davranış. [Organizational behavior] Ankara, Turkey, Nobel Publications.
- Hoy, Wayne K. & Miskel, G. Cecil (2012). Educational Administration, Theory, Research and Practice, (Translation Ed. Selahattin Turan) Ankara, Turkey, Nobel Publications.
- Korkmaz, S.(2006). Sosyal öğrenme kuramı, Eğitim Psikolojisi, [Social learning theory, Educational Psychology] (Ed. Binnur Yeşilyaprak). Ankara, Turkey, Pegem A Publications.
- Luthans, F., Youssef, C. M., & Avolio, B. J. (2006). Psychological capital: Developing the human competitive edge. Oxford University Press.
- Myers, D., G. (2017), *Sosyal psikoloji*, [Social psychology] (Translation Ed. Serap Akfırat). Ankara, Turkey, Nobel Publications.
- Narcıkara, I. (2017). Increasingly ascending positivity in organizations: positive organizational scholarship perspective. Journal of Behavior at Work - JB@W Vol.2(1), 1-33.
- Özen, Kutanis, R., Oruç, E. (2014). A theoretical investigation on positive organizational behavior and positive psychological capital. The Journal of Happiness & Well-Being, 2014, 2(2), 145-159.
- Özen, Kutanis, R., Yıldız, E. (2014). The relationship between positive psychology and positive organizational behavior and an evaluation on positive organizational behavior dimensions Suleyman Demirel University The Journal of Visionary Vol.5, No.11., pp.135-154.
- Robbins S., P. & Judge, T. A (2012). Örgütsel davranış, [Organizational behavior] (Translation Ed. İnci Erdem) Ankara, Turkey, Nobel Publications.
- Senemoğlu, N. (1997). Gelişim, öğrenme ve öğretim. [Development, learning and teaching] H.U. Publications of the Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Sciences. Ankara, Turkey
- Shaughnessy, J.J., Zechmeister, E.B. & Zechmeister, J.S. (2020). Psikolojide araştırma yöntemleri [Research methods in psychology] (Translation Ed. İlyas Göz). Ankara, Turkey, Nobel Publications.
- Slavin, E. R. (2013). Eğitim psikolojisi [Educational psychology theory and practice] (Translation Ed. Galip Yüksel) Ankara, Turkey, Nobel Publications.
- Şanlı, Ö. (2009). The effect of positive management approach on the success of students at primary schools. (Sample of Malatya City), Master Thesis Fırat University Institute of Social Sciences Educational Administration Supervision Planning and Economics, Turkey,
- Tösten, R. (2015). Examination of teachers' perceptions on positive psychological capital. Gaziantep University Ph.D. Thesis, Department of Educational Sciences Supervisor. Gaziantep, Turkey,
- Yıldırım, A. & Şimşek, H. (2008). *Sosyal bilimlerde nitel araştırma yöntemleri* [Qualitative research methods in the social sciences] Ankara, Turkey, Seçkin Publications.